

Versioned Archive and Review of Biotic
Interactions and Taxon Names Found within
globalbioticinteractions/fmnh
hash://md5/8eee18758a895132a5b26c6ae07e10de

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Abstract

Life on Earth is sustained by complex interactions between organisms and their environment. These biotic interactions can be captured in datasets and published digitally. We present a review and archiving process for such an openly accessible digital interactions dataset of known origin and discuss its outcome. The dataset under review, named `globalbioticinteractions/fmnh`, has fingerprint hash://md5/8eee18758a895132a5b26c6ae07e10de, is 1.16GiB in size and contains 128,731 interactions with 10 unique types of associations (e.g., `adjacentTo`) between 22,373 primary taxa (e.g., *Trichobius joblingi* Wenzel, 1966) and 33,890 associated taxa (e.g., *Carollia perspicillata*). This report includes detailed summaries of interaction data, a taxonomic review from multiple catalogs, and an archived version of the dataset from which the reviews are derived.

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Introduction

Data Review and Archive

Data review and archiving can be a time-consuming process, especially when done manually. This review report aims to help facilitate both activities. It automates the archiving of datasets, including Darwin Core archives, and is a citable backup of a version of the dataset. Additionally, an automatic review of species interaction claims made in the dataset is generated and registered with Global Biotic Interactions (J. H. Poelen, Simons, and Mungall 2014).

This review includes summary statistics about, and observations about, the dataset under review :

Field Museum of Natural History (Botany) Bryophyte Collection -
Version 11.9 https://fmipt.fieldmuseum.org/ipt/archive.do?r=fmnh_bryophyte
2026-06-02T14:58:00.016Z Field Museum of Natural History
(Botany) Fungi Collection - Version 4.14 https://fmipt.fieldmuseum.org/ipt/archive.do?r=fmnh_fungi
2026-06-02T14:58:00.016Z Field Museum of Natural History
(Botany) Lichen Collection - Version 2.15 https://fmipt.fieldmuseum.org/ipt/archive.do?r=fmnh_lichens
2026-06-02T14:58:00.016Z Field Museum of Natural History
(Botany) Pteridophyte Collection - Version 2.9 https://fmipt.fieldmuseum.org/ipt/archive.do?r=fmnh_pt
2026-06-02T14:58:00.016Z Field Museum of Natural History
(Botany) Seed Plant Collection - Version 11.16 https://fmipt.fieldmuseum.org/ipt/archive.do?r=fmnh_seed
2026-06-02T14:58:00.016Z Field Museum of Natural History (Zool-
ogy) Bird Collection - Version 14.22 https://fmipt.fieldmuseum.org/ipt/archive.do?r=fm_birds
2026-06-02T14:58:00.016Z Field Museum of Natural History (Zool-
ogy) Insect, Arachnid and Myriapod Collection - Version 12.64
https://fmipt.fieldmuseum.org/ipt/archive.do?r=fmnh_insects
2026-06-02T14:58:00.016Z Field Museum of Natural History (Zool-
ogy) Invertebrate Collection - Version 18.54 https://fmipt.fieldmuseum.org/ipt/archive.do?r=fmnh_inver

Methods

The review is performed through programmatic scripts that leverage tools like Preston (Elliott et al. 2025), Elton (Kuhn, Poelen, and Leinweber 2025), Nomer (Salim and Poelen 2025), globinizer (J. Poelen, Seltmann, and Mietchen 2024) combined with third-party tools like grep, mlr, tail and head.

Table 1: Tools used in this review process

tool name	version
preston	0.11.1
elton	0.16.11
nomer	0.6.5
globinizer	0.4.0
mlr	6.0.0
jq	1.6
yq	4.25.3
pandoc	3.1.6.1
duckdb	1.3.1
mapserver	7.6.4

The review process can be described in the form of the script below ¹.

```
# get versioned copy of the dataset (size approx. 1.16GiB) under review
elton pull globalbioticinteractions/fmnh

# generate review notes
elton review globalbioticinteractions/fmnh \
  > review.tsv

# export indexed interaction records
elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/fmnh \
  > interactions.tsv

# export names and align them with the Catalogue of Life using Nomer
elton names globalbioticinteractions/fmnh \
```

¹Note that you have to first get the data (e.g., via `elton pull globalbioticinteractions/fmnh`) before being able to generate reviews (e.g., `elton review globalbioticinteractions/fmnh`), extract interaction claims (e.g., `elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/fmnh`), or list taxonomic names (e.g., `elton names globalbioticinteractions/fmnh`)

```
| nomer append col \  
> name-alignment.tsv
```

or visually, in a process diagram.

Figure 1: Review Process Overview

You can find a copy of the full review script at `check-data.sh`. See also GitHub and Codeberg.

Results

In the following sections, the results of the review are summarized ². Then, links to the detailed review reports are provided.

Files

An extensive list of files produced as part of the review process can be found in Appendix A. Review Files.

Archived Dataset

Note that `data.zip` file in this archive contains the complete, unmodified archived dataset under review.

Biotic Interactions

Figure 2: Biotic Interaction Data Model

²Disclaimer: The results in this review should be considered friendly, yet naive, notes from an unsophisticated robot. Please keep that in mind when considering the review results.

In this review, biotic interactions (or biotic associations) are modeled as a primary (aka subject, source) organism interacting with an associate (aka object, target) organism. The dataset under review classified the primary/associate organisms with specific taxa. The primary and associate organisms The kind of interaction is documented as an interaction type.

The dataset under review, named `globalbioticinteractions/fmnh`, has fingerprint hash://md5/8eee18758a895132a5b26c6ae07e10de, is 1.16GiB in size and contains 128,731 interactions with 10 unique types of associations (e.g., `adjacentTo`) between 22,373 primary taxa (e.g., *Trichobius joblingi* Wenzel, 1966) and 33,890 associated taxa (e.g., *Carollia perspicillata*).

An exhaustive list of indexed interaction claims can be found in gzipped csv, tsv, geopackage and parquet archives. To facilitate discovery, a preview of claims available in the gzipped html page at `indexed-interactions.html.gz` are shown below.

The exhaustive list was used to create the following data summaries below.

Table 2: Sample of Indexed Interaction Claims

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Falcaustra	endoparasiteOf	Kalophrynus meizon	Stephen R. Goldberg
Seuratascaris numidica Sprent, 1985	endoparasiteOf	Staurois parvus	Stephen R. Goldberg
Oswaldocruzia	endoparasiteOf	Kalophrynus meizon	Stephen R. Goldberg
Kiricephalus pattoni	endoparasiteOf	Chaperina fusca	Stephen R. Goldberg

Table 3: Most Frequently Mentioned Interaction Types (up to 20 most frequent)

interactionTypeName	count
adjacentTo	91922
ectoparasiteOf	34989
interactsWith	882
parasiteOf	564
hasHost	175
visitsFlowersOf	150
endoparasiteOf	27
eats	11
hostOf	10

interactionTypeName	count
eatenBy	1

Table 4: Most Frequently Mentioned Primary Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	count
Trichobius joblingi Wenzel, 1966	2639
Marchantiophyta Stotler & Crand.-Stotl.	1516
Megistopoda aranea (Coquillt, 1899)	1287
Megistopoda proxima (Sguy, 1926)	1162
Trichobius parasiticus Gervais, 1844	1012
Strebla guajiro (Garcia & Casal, 1965)	1000
Strebla wiedemanni Kolenati, 1856	946
Aspidoptera phyllostomatis (Perty, 1833)	820
Speiseria ambigua Kessel, 1925	779
Fungus indet.	730
Aspidoptera falcata Wenzel, 1976	720
Hippoboscoidea	609
Paratrachobius longicrus (Miranda Ribeiro, 1907)	597
Trichobius costalimai Guimares, 1938	573
Nycterophilia coxata Ferris, 1916	543
Usnea Dill. ex Adans.	515
Ixodida Leach, 1815	505
Trichobius dugesii Townsend, 1891	492
Trichobioides perspicillatus (Pessoa & Galvao, 1937)	422

Table 5: Most Frequently Mentioned Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

targetTaxonName	count
Carollia perspicillata	2692
Artibeus jamaicensis	1740
Desmodus rotundus	1564
Sturnira lilium	1527
ground	1397
tree	1221
rocks	1155
Phyllostomus discolor	1123
log	1001
dead wood	831

targetTaxonName	count
Pteronotus parnellii	792
soil	791
Carollia brevicauda	776
trees	671
beach	651
Carollia perspicillata azteca	649
leaf litter	638
Glossophaga soricina	629
Artiodactyla	618

Table 6: Most Frequent Interactions between Primary and Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	count
Trichobius joblingi Wenzel, 1966	ectoparasiteOf	Carollia perspicillata	1377
Megistopoda proxima (Séguy, 1926)	ectoparasiteOf	Sturnira lilium	906
Megistopoda aranea (Coquillétt, 1899)	ectoparasiteOf	Artibeus jamaicensis	793
Trichobius parasiticus Gervais, 1844	ectoparasiteOf	Desmodus rotundus	775
Strebla wiedemanni Kolenati, 1856	ectoparasiteOf	Desmodus rotundus	697
Strebla guajiro (Garcia & Casal, 1965)	ectoparasiteOf	Carollia perspicillata	570
Aspidoptera falcata Wenzel, 1976	ectoparasiteOf	Sturnira lilium	520
Aspidoptera phyllostomatis (Perty, 1833)	ectoparasiteOf	Artibeus jamaicensis	504
Trichobius costalimai Guimarães, 1938	ectoparasiteOf	Phyllostomus discolor	454

sourceTaxonName	interactionType	targetTaxonName	count
Speiseria ambigua Kessel, 1925	ectoparasiteOf	Carollia perspicillata	366
Paratrichobius longicrus (Miranda Ribeiro, 1907)	ectoparasiteOf	Artibeus litoratus	351
Trichobioides perspicillatus (Pessoa & Galvao, 1937)	ectoparasiteOf	Phyllostomus discolor	340
Trichobius joblingi Wenzel, 1966	ectoparasiteOf	Carollia perspicillata azteca	317
Trichobius caecus Edwards, 1918	ectoparasiteOf	Pteronotus parnellii	292
Strebila hertigi Wenzel, 1966	ectoparasiteOf	Phyllostomus discolor	284
Nycterophilia coxata Ferris, 1916	ectoparasiteOf	Leptonycteris curasoae	272
Trichobius dugesii Townsend, 1891	ectoparasiteOf	Glossophaga soricina	259
Trichobius joblingi Wenzel, 1966	ectoparasiteOf	Carollia brevicauda	256
Trichobius longipes (Rudow, 1871)	ectoparasiteOf	Phyllostomus hastatus	244

Interaction Networks

The figures below provide a graph view on the dataset under review. The first shows a summary network on the kingdom level, and the second shows how interactions on the family level. It is important to note that both network graphs were first aligned taxonomically using the Catalogue of Life. Please refer to the original (or verbatim) taxonomic names for a more original view on the interaction data.

You can download the indexed dataset under review at [indexed-interactions.csv.gz](#). A tab-separated file can be found at [indexed-interactions.tsv.gz](#)

Figure 3: Interactions on taxonomic kingdom rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life [download svg](#)

Figure 4: Interactions on the taxonomic family rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life. [download svg](#)

Geospatial Distribution

If geospatial information was extracted from the dataset under review, the map below will show their distribution. These maps were generated using MapServer (McKenna et al. 2025) tools configured via map configuration indexed-interactions.map :

```
MAP
  SIZE 1600 800
  EXTENT -180 -90 180 90
  PROJECTION
    "init=epsg:4326"
  END
  LAYER # MODIS WMS map from NASA
    NAME "modis_nasa"
    TYPE RASTER
    OFFSITE 0 0 0
    STATUS ON
    CONNECTIONTYPE WMS
    CONNECTION "https://gibs.earthdata.nasa.gov/wms/epsg4326/best/wms.cgi?"

  METADATA
    "wms_srs" "EPSG:4326"
    "wms_name" "OSM_Land_Water_Map"
    "wms_server_version" "1.1.1"
    "wms_format" "image/jpeg"
  END
  CLASS
    STYLE
      COLOR 232 232 232
      OUTLINECOLOR 32 32 32
    END
  END
  LAYER
    NAME "indexed-interactions"
    TYPE POLYGON
    STATUS ON
    CONNECTIONTYPE OGR
    CONNECTION "indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg"
    DATA "indexed-interactions-h3"
    CLASS
      STYLE
        COLORRANGE 253.0 231.0 37.0 32.0 164.0 134.0
        DATARANGE 0.3010299956639812 3.574147064150723
        RANGEITEM "log_number_of_records"
```

```

        OUTLINECOLOR 0 0 0
      END
    END
  END
END

```


Figure 5: Hexagonal grid cells indicate that interactions claims are available for selected geospatial area: light yellow means relatively fewer claims, dark green relatively more claims.

Associated data can be found in the geopackage files at `indexed-interactions.gpkg` for point data and `indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg` for data clustered in geospatial h3 hexagonals.

Learn more about the structure of this download at GloBI website, by opening a GitHub issue, or by sending an email.

Another way to discover the dataset under review is by searching for it on the GloBI website.

Taxonomic Alignment

As part of the review, all names are aligned against various name catalogs (e.g., col, ncbi, discoverlife, gbif, itis, wfo, mdd, tpt, pbdb, and worms). These alignments can help review name usage or aid in selecting of a suitable taxonomic name resource.

Table 7: Sample of Name Alignments

providedName	relationName	resolvedCatalogName	resolvedName
Tall	NONE	col	Tall

providedName	relationName	resolvedCatalogName	resolvedName
Ft peat over sand	NONE	col	Ft peat over sand
Cm diam trunk bog pine	NONE	col	Cm diam trunk bog pine
Diam trunk	NONE	col	Diam trunk

Table 8: Distribution of Taxonomic Ranks of Aligned Names by Catalog. Names that were not aligned with a catalog are counted as NAs. So, the total number of unaligned names for a catalog will be listed in their NA row.

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
col	NA	22019
col	class	27
col	family	166
col	form	4
col	genus	2026
col	gigaclass	1
col	infraorder	4
col	kingdom	3
col	order	40
col	phylum	19
col	species	22595
col	subclass	4
col	subfamily	7
col	subgenus	38
col	suborder	3
col	subphylum	1
col	subspecies	940
col	superfamily	4
col	tribe	5
col	variety	214
discoverlife	NA	47706
gbif	NA	21468
gbif	class	25
gbif	family	171
gbif	form	29
gbif	genus	2047
gbif	kingdom	4
gbif	order	49
gbif	phylum	19
gbif	species	22931
gbif	subspecies	1093
gbif	variety	469

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
itis	NA	37547
itis	class	24
itis	division	8
itis	family	161
itis	genus	1335
itis	infraorder	2
itis	kingdom	3
itis	order	56
itis	phylum	13
itis	species	7941
itis	subclass	9
itis	subfamily	6
itis	subgenus	5
itis	suborder	3
itis	subphylum	2
itis	subspecies	396
itis	superclass	1
itis	superfamily	3
itis	variety	217
mdd	NA	47705
ncbi	NA	32202
ncbi	clade	8
ncbi	class	23
ncbi	family	157
ncbi	forma	1
ncbi	forma specialis	2
ncbi	genus	1854
ncbi	infraorder	4
ncbi	kingdom	2
ncbi	order	54
ncbi	phylum	14
ncbi	section	1
ncbi	species	13126
ncbi	subclass	10
ncbi	subfamily	8
ncbi	subgenus	9
ncbi	suborder	2
ncbi	subphylum	1
ncbi	subspecies	192
ncbi	subtribe	1
ncbi	superclass	1
ncbi	superfamily	5
ncbi	tribe	3
ncbi	varietas	37

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
pbdb	NA	45743
pbdb	class	28
pbdb	family	126
pbdb	genus	693
pbdb	informal	2
pbdb	infraorder	3
pbdb	kingdom	3
pbdb	order	52
pbdb	phylum	18
pbdb	species	1010
pbdb	subclass	8
pbdb	subfamily	8
pbdb	subgenus	2
pbdb	suborder	5
pbdb	subspecies	3
pbdb	superclass	1
pbdb	superfamily	4
pbdb	superorder	3
pbdb	superphylum	2
pbdb	tribe	2
pbdb	unranked clade	10
tpt	NA	46510
tpt	family	3
tpt	genus	130
tpt	order	2
tpt	species	1060
wfo	NA	39129
wfo	family	39
wfo	form	3
wfo	genus	927
wfo	phylum	1
wfo	section	1
wfo	species	7332
wfo	subsection	1
wfo	subspecies	227
wfo	tribe	1
wfo	variety	187
worms	NA	42455
worms	class	24
worms	family	139
worms	genus	925
worms	gigaclass	1
worms	infraclass	1
worms	infraorder	3

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
worms	kingdom	3
worms	order	52
worms	phylum	11
worms	phylum (division)	7
worms	species	3905
worms	subclass	8
worms	subfamily	2
worms	suborder	3
worms	subphylum	2
worms	subspecies	167
worms	superclass	1
worms	superfamily	4
worms	variety	53

Table 9: Name relationship types per catalog. Name relationship type “NONE” means that a name was not recognized by the associated catalog. “SAME_AS” indicates either a “HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME” or “SYNONYM_OF” name relationship type. We recognize that “SYNONYM_OF” encompasses many types of nomenclatural synonymies (ICZN 1999) (e.g., junior synonym, senior synonyms).

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
col	NONE	29069
col	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	20409
col	SYNONYM_OF	15366
discoverlife	NONE	58064
gbif	NONE	28534
gbif	SYNONYM_OF	16952
gbif	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	24664
itis	NONE	45197
itis	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	10128
itis	SYNONYM_OF	3150
mdd	NONE	57219
mdd	SYNONYM_OF	31
mdd	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	740
ncbi	NONE	39756
ncbi	SAME_AS	15694
ncbi	SYNONYM_OF	2736
ncbi	COMMON_NAME_OF	7
pbdb	NONE	55019
pbdb	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	2873

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
pbdb	SYNONYM_OF	247
tpt	NONE	56749
tpt	SYNONYM_OF	103
tpt	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	1212
wfo	NONE	46807
wfo	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	7962
wfo	SYNONYM_OF	4271
wfo	HAS_UNCHECKED_NAME	1612
worms	NONE	51815
worms	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	5817
worms	SYNONYM_OF	1406

Table 10: List of Available Name Alignment Reports

catalog name	alignment results
col	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
ncbi	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
discoverlife	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
gbif	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
itis	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
wfo	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
mdd	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
tpt	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
pbdb	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
worms	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)

Additional Reviews

Elton, Nomer, and other tools may have difficulties interpreting existing species interaction datasets. Or, they may misbehave, or otherwise show unexpected behavior. As part of the review process, detailed review notes are kept that

document possibly misbehaving, or confused, review bots. An sample of review notes associated with this review can be found below.

Table 11: First few lines in the review notes.

reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
2026-06-04T01:22:18Z	note	found unresolved reference [c8bdd05a-1fad-44c3-96fa-367fb96ec0de]
2026-06-04T01:22:18Z	note	found unresolved reference [https://arctos.database.museum/guid/CHAS:Bird:18783]
2026-06-04T01:22:18Z	note	found unresolved reference [https://arctos.database.museum/guid/CHAS:Bird:18830]
2026-06-04T01:22:18Z	note	found unresolved reference [https://arctos.database.museum/guid/CHAS:Bird:8302]

In addition, you can find the most frequently occurring notes in the table below.

Table 12: Most frequently occurring review notes, if any.

reviewComment	count
found unresolved reference [c8bdd05a-1fad-44c3-96fa-367fb96ec0de]	1
found unresolved reference [https://arctos.database.museum/guid/CHAS:Bird:18783]	1
found unresolved reference [https://arctos.database.museum/guid/CHAS:Bird:18830]	1
found unresolved reference [https://arctos.database.museum/guid/CHAS:Bird:8302]	1

For additional information on review notes, please have a look at the first 500 Review Notes in html format or the download full gzipped csv or tsv archives.

GloBI Review Badge

As part of the review, a review badge is generated. This review badge can be included in webpages to indicate the review status of the dataset under review.

³Up-to-date status of the GloBI Review Badge can be retrieved from the GloBI Review Depot

Figure 6: Picture of a GloBI Review Badge ³

Note that if the badge is green, no review notes were generated. If the badge is yellow, the review bots may need some help with interpreting the species interaction data.

GloBI Index Badge

If the dataset under review has been registered with GloBI, and has been successfully indexed by GloBI, the GloBI Index Status Badge will turn green. This means that the dataset under review was indexed by GloBI and is available through GloBI services and derived data products.

Figure 7: Picture of a GloBI Index Badge ⁴

If you'd like to keep track of reviews or index status of the dataset under review, please visit GloBI's dataset index ⁵ for badge examples.

Discussion

This review and archive provides a means of creating citable versions of datasets that change frequently. This may be useful for dataset managers, including natural history collection data managers, as a backup archive of a shared Darwin Core archive. It also serves as a means of creating a trackable citation for the dataset in an automated way, while also including some information about the contents of the dataset.

This review aims to provide a perspective on the dataset to aid in understanding of species interaction claims discovered. However, it is important to note that this review does *not* assess the quality of the dataset. Instead, it serves as an indication of the open-ness⁶ and FAIRness (Wilkinson et al. 2016; Trekels et al. 2023) of the dataset: to perform this review, the data was likely openly available, **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable. The current Open-FAIR assessment is qualitative, and a more quantitative approach can be implemented with specified measurement units.

⁴Up-to-date status of the GloBI Index Badge can be retrieved from GloBI's API

⁵At time of writing (2026-06-04) the version of the GloBI dataset index was available at <https://globalbioticinteractions.org/datasets>

⁶According to <http://opendefinition.org/>: "Open data is data that can be freely used, re-used and redistributed by anyone - subject only, at most, to the requirement to attribute and sharealike."

This report also showcases the reuse of machine-actionable (meta)data, something highly recommended by the FAIR Data Principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016). Making (meta)data machine-actionable enables more precise processing by computers, enabling even naive review bots like Nomer and Elton to interpret the data effectively. This capability is crucial for not just automating the generation of reports, but also for facilitating seamless data exchanges, promoting interoperability.

Acknowledgements

We thank the many humans that created us and those who created and maintained the data, software and other intellectual resources that were used for producing this review. In addition, we are grateful for the natural resources providing the basis for these human and bot activities. Also, thanks to <https://github.com/zygoballus> for helping improve the layout of the review tables.

Author contributions

Nomer was responsible for name alignments. Elton carried out dataset extraction, and generated the review notes. Preston tracked, versioned, and packaged, the dataset under review.

Appendix A. Review Files

The following files are produced in this review:

filename	description
biblio.bib	list of bibliographic reference of this review
check-dataset.sh	data review workflow/process as expressed in a bash script
data.zip	a versioned archive of the data under review
HEAD	the digital signature of the data under review
index.docx	review in MS Word format
index.html	review in HTML format
index.md	review in Pandoc markdown format
index.pdf	review in PDF format

filename	description
indexed-citations.csv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped comma-separated values file format
indexed-citations.html.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interactions claims in gzipped html file format
indexed-citations.tsv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions-col-family-col-family.svg	network diagram showing the taxon family to taxon family interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions-col-kingdom-col-kingdom.svg	network diagram showing the taxon kingdom to taxon kingdom interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions.csv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions.html.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-interactions.tsv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions.parquet	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-interactions.png	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review plotted on a map
indexed-interactions.map	mapserver configuration to plot species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review on a map

filename	description
indexed-interactions.gpkg	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg	geospatially clustered h3 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-sample.csv	list of species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions-sample.html	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in html format
indexed-interactions-sample.tsv	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
indexed-names.csv.gz	taxonomic names indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-names.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-col.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-col.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-itis.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-worms.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-sample.csv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
indexed-names-sample.html	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in html format
indexed-names-sample.tsv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
interaction.svg	diagram summarizing the data model used to index species interaction claims
nanopub-sample.trig	first 500 species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
nanopub.trig.gz	species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
process.svg	diagram summarizing the data review processing workflow
prov.nq	origin of the dataset under review as expressed in rdf/nquads

filename	description
review.csv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
review.html.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped html format
review.tsv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
review-sample.csv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
review-sample.html	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in html format
review-sample.tsv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
review.svg	a review badge generated as part of the dataset review process
zenodo.json	metadata of this review expressed in Zenodo record metadata

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